

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
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Neural Network-based fingerprinting for background music identification

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Dedication

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Abstract

Identifying background music in video-on-demand (VoD) content is complex, given the low background music levels, fluctuating dialogue, and various forms of audio degradation. Moreover, the high presence of sound effects (SFX) in VoD audiovisual increases the errors in identifications since these SFX are often used in multiple tracks, leading to wrong identifications of music in the case where a query and a reference share an SFX, but the music is different. Traditional audio fingerprinting is significantly challenged in this scenario, and a new approach is needed to deal with this data type.

This thesis addresses some of these challenges in improving music identification in VoD content. The contributions of this thesis can be summarised as follows: First, I present CueSet, a carefully annotated dataset with real-world examples of VoD audio issues encountered in BMAT customers' data. This dataset serves as a test dataset for VoD music identification. Second, I developed a new data pipeline integrating advanced audio augmentation techniques, including adding speech and dialogue features, into Neural Audio fingerprinting, the open-source SOTA audio fingerprinting system. This aims to simulate the challenging conditions typical of VoD environments more accurately. Finally, I conducted three comprehensive experiments using this data augmentation pipeline to train a neural network-based fingerprinting model. These efforts led to substantial improvements over existing baselines, with a +29.9% increase in precision, a +28.3% improvement in recall, and a +28% enhancement in F1-score in recognizing music in VoD content. However, the extensive use of augmentations introduced additional training complexities, requiring precise model tuning to achieve optimal performance.

Our experiments show that mixing music with speech as an augmentation during training effectively improves the robustness of background music identification in VoD content. Other audio degradation techniques also helped to improve the system's robustness, but their potential is only shown after a few adjustments in the model. By emphasising the need for good-quality datasets and domain-specific,

proper augmentations, we are taking significant steps towards improving audio identification technologies in industry avenues, offering hope for more effective solutions.

Keywords: Audio Fingerprinting; background music identification; Dataset; Neural Networks; Contrastive learning

Chapter 1

Introduction

Music Recognition Technology(MRT) is an important and active research field that aims to recognize music titles with high accuracy within a short response time. It does that by recognizing audio signals and comparing them to a database of previously known songs. Recognition is a big deal for the music industry: it allows the creators to get paid their dues and powers search engines or content analysis systems of various kinds.

The spread of music on various platforms and media formats emphasises the importance of a more competent and robust recognition system. Nevertheless, issues remain, such as recognising background music in audiovisual content. These tracks are typically weak, buried in sound effects, dialogue, and degradations, so they are difficult to separate from one another, which makes genuinely identifying the sound tough.

This dissertation addresses the challenges of identifying background music in audiovisual content. Current MRT systems need help in this domain, as they often fail to accurately detect and recognise low-volume tracks that blend with dialogue, sound effects, and other music layers. I believe that significant advancements can be made by leveraging techniques such as:

- **Advanced Filtering Techniques:** Developing sophisticated algorithms to

isolate background music from overlapping sounds.

- **Machine Learning Models:** Training models on diverse datasets to enhance recognition capabilities, particularly for faint and mixed tracks.
- **Robust Datasets:** Creating comprehensive collections of audio samples encompassing various background music scenarios for training and testing purposes.
- **Integration with Audiovisual Content Analysis:** Combining MRT with other audiovisual analysis tools to leverage context and improve identification within the broader soundscape of media content.

By tackling these challenges, we aim to contribute to the development of more effective MRT systems that can accurately identify background music in audiovisual content. This, in turn, will support fair compensation for creators, enable comprehensive content analysis, and ultimately enhance our overall understanding and enjoyment of music.

1.1 Motivation

The primary motivation for this work is in the light that reliable music identification, especially regarding background music within audiovisual content, is valuable as it enables several use cases:

- **Fair Compensation to Creators:** Giving music creators the credit and compensation they deserve is essential, mainly when their music is used in audiovisual content in the background.
- **Comprehensive Content Analysis:** Correctly identifying music enables comprehensive content analysis, which provides a richer understanding of music's role and impact within different media formats.
- **Enhanced User Experience:** Better music identification skills enable superior user experience as they allow users to use functionalities like search

on a small drone engine, feature-rich discovery of the contents, and intuitive discovery of the contents.

Music recognition technology (MRT) has made giant strides in recent years but still remains a complex challenge when it comes to identifying background music at low volume that overlaps other sounds. These issues are barriers against which the best current systems could be more effective.

The scientific community has come a long way in identifying the music being played using audio fingerprinting and machine learning techniques. Since then, music recognition has been built on the principle of audio fingerprinting by forming unique 'fingerprints' of songs, which are characteristic patterns that can be identified quickly and accurately. While traditional methods are often faster, deep learning models such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) provide superior accuracy and robustness. They work exceptionally well at recognizing nuanced audio patterns, perfectly fitting for background music detection and recognition in actual audio environments.

The motivation behind this research is the need to tackle these challenges and help improve more reliable MRT systems. I will investigate ways to improve the identification of background music in audiovisual content by working on advanced augmentation techniques, machine learning models, and robust datasets integrated with audiovisual content analysis.

This research will serve music creators and content analysts, ultimately enhancing a broadened & educated musical palette for everyone.

1.2 Cue sheets

Cue sheets are invaluable tools in music recognition, particularly in broadcasting and video-on-demand (VoD) contexts. These structured documents provide metadata about the music used in audiovisual productions, typically including song titles, composers, publishers, and usage timestamps. While cue sheets offer a high level of

detail and can significantly aid in music identification, they often must be completed or corrected. These inconsistencies limit their effectiveness and create challenges for accurately identifying music. Despite these limitations, cue sheets remain a crucial starting point for music identification. However, there is a pressing need for further research to automate their creation more accurately, ensuring that researchers and industry professionals can use them in conjunction with other identification methods and highlighting the potential for improvement in music identification.

1.3 About BMAT and resCUE project

1.3.1 About BMAT

BMAT¹ plays a key role in the music identification industry, providing customers with real-time music monitoring and identification services globally. A crucial part of BMAT's work involves accurately identifying background music in television, film, and other audiovisual productions. This task is intricate due to the soft sound levels of background music, its merging with dialogues and other sounds, and the wide range of composers involved in different media.

BMAT's expertise extends beyond basic recognition; they specialize in identifying music in television productions and other audiovisual content. To benefit copyright owners and content creators, BMAT has developed new tools that streamline the processes of identifying songs and reporting them.

- **Reportal** is a flagship product that automates the cues-sheet creation process for broadcasters, significantly reducing manual labour and minimizing claims from Collective Management Organizations (CMOs). By automating this crucial step, BMAT enhances accuracy and efficiency in royalty distribution.
- **Cued** It is a tool designed for companies and music publishers that offers a versatile approach to cue sheet generation. Users can create cue sheets man-

¹<https://bmat.com>

ually, from Edit Decision Lists (EDLs), or directly from media files, catering to various workflows and data sources.

These tools and BMAT's broader expertise have positioned them as a key player in facilitating accurate royalty distribution and copyright management within the music industry.

1.3.2 The resCUE Project

The current project, resCUE (SAV-20221147), addresses copyright management issues in the Spanish audiovisual industry. The cue-sheet-based system could be more efficient and prone to mistakes, which causes under-reporting and non-payment of royalties. BMAT's resCUE has an answer using automating and digitizing the process with the application of artificial intelligence (AI) technology for identifying music within audiovisual productions and providing accurate information about these musical works with their rights holders. This invention will save time for producers, increase transparency, and enhance compensation for artists, thus changing how copyright management is done in the Spanish audiovisual industry.

Finally, BMAT's resCUE is an exciting venture that employs creative technologies to improve efficiency and fairness in compensating creators while protecting stakeholders' interests in the audiovisual industry. Through streamlining procedures and promoting accountability, this undertaking strengthens BMAT's foothold within its market niche and creates a window for collaboration with partners who can help it grow further.

This thesis aims to build on these advancements by developing a system that uses audio fingerprinting and machine learning to reliably identify background music, regardless of the complexity of the signals. This study could help BMAT enhance its tools' precision and effectiveness, benefiting authors, copyright owners, and the broader music industry. Ultimately, it represents a significant step toward solving the puzzle of music recognition and expanding the limits of musical knowledge retrieval systems.

Chapter 2

Scientific Background

2.1 Audio Fingerprinting

AFP is a ubiquitous technology for robust audio content identification and retrieval, combined with automatically or manually generated metadata describing the samples. This is crucial for music recognition, copyright protection, and monitoring of this content. As the demand for background music from various areas, such as television broadcasting and VoD content, has increased in recent years, our study will mention the fundamentals of how automatic identification of b/gm could be achieved. This process consists of several stages, each facilitating accuracy and speed identification.

- **Feature Extraction:** The initial phase in audio fingerprinting is feature extraction, where an analysis of the audio signal results in a concise and distinct representation, which we call an Audio Fingerprint. This could involve segmenting audio and collecting features such as frequency patterns, energy levels, and temporal information that describe its content. In our case, background music should be detected between overlapped dialogue / sound FX or noise, meaning feature extraction must be robust and quick in this complex audio environment while streaming VoD.

- **Indexing:** After extracting features, we must construct a high-speed and effective structure from all audio fingerprints to sustain quick retrieval. Organizing this way is also necessary to quickly compare the fingerprints you have extracted and all stored in an extensive database. We typically manage fingerprints with a hashing function or use some tree-based structure to provide quick localization and comparison of relevant entries. While necessary for low-effort live audio fingerprinting applications, this research focuses mainly on optimizing fingerprints so that matches can be made reliably when content may feature VoD-like noisy and dynamic conditions.
- **Matching:** Matching is the basic concept of audio fingerprinting, which matches a query fingerprint to any indexed fingerprints on available databases to find correspondence. It is called Match. The method uses a similarity level threshold to define positive identification. Identifying background music in VoD content is challenging because its sound signals are combined with other signals. The study will also consider these precision-recall curves to maximize recognition accuracy and report matching thresholds.
- **Post-Processing and Verification:** Post-processing is done on potential matches to count the results and eliminate false positives. You should look up other metadata and validate pieces or complete secondary checks. While post-processing is an indelible component of the entire system, this dissertation focuses mainly on improvements in earlier stages, namely feature extraction and matching (all to foster better retrieval of background music fragments from VoD acoustic environments).

This work aims to significantly advance the reliability of audio identification by refining key processes in audio fingerprinting, particularly in challenging scenarios where background music must be identified against the backdrop of other competing audio elements.

2.1.1 First approaches

The Philips Fingerprint method, developed by Haitsma and Kalker [1] in 2002, is one of the earliest and most essential concepts for audio fingerprinting. This is a way of extracting energy across frequency bands in an audio signal. The attempt to separate individual frames begins by segmenting an audio signal into small, overlapping, short, time-interval pieces. A Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) transforms every frame into the Frequency domain. Energy is calculated in pre-defined frequency bands over each frame. The energy values are then quantized to produce binary fingerprints that can be concatenated to create a compact audio signal representation. This method is robust against audio distortions such as compression, noise and equalization because it captures the main characteristics of an audio signal in its frequency domain. This has been very helpful in the development of audio-solid fingerprinting systems.

Another method to influence or was another landmark in the technology of audio fingerprinting is called The Shazam Fingerprint method, which Avery Wang introduced in 2003 [1]. This approach uses the idea of looking for audio clips using spectral peaks. It begins by converting an audio signal to a spectrogram — the intensity of frequencies over time. This algorithm naively picks the local maxima in the spectrogram to find prominent spectral peaks. These peaks for each frame are then used to generate time-frequency hashes capturing the audio signal's frequency and temporal information. These hashes are kept in the database and used to match input audio queries by comparing their hash sequences with db sequences. Because the Shazam method is so fast and accurate, it makes a promising approach for real-time music identification used in commercial applications.

2.1.2 AFP from Local descriptors

When talking about energy-based fingerprints in the frequency band, it is necessary to start from Haitsma and Kalker's [2] groundbreaking work. They formulated the Philips fingerprint, which is composed of hash strings created from energies of 33 bark-scaled frequency bands. These strings are derived from the sign of energy dif-

ferences across time and frequency. The technique compares energy values between neighbouring sub-fingerprints as well as bands. In their enhanced search algorithm, candidate positions are produced on the basis that one sub-fingerprint will match the best position in the database. Therefore, only those positions must be checked where one out of 256 sub-fingerprints matches perfectly, making this method suitable for real-world applications with large databases.

Ever since the advent of the Philips fingerprinting technique [3, 2], many methods have been proposed to improve it. These approaches aim at making it more resistant to various alterations like pitch shifting and time scaling; scalability and efficiency also being considered.

For audio fingerprinting, Baluja and Covell [4] modified a computer vision method. Overlapping time slices were used to process the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) representation of audio; wavelets were computed from these slices, and then their magnitudes were compared. The 200 most prominent wavelets were compressed into individual sign bits representing 200-byte values using Min-Hash for nearest neighbour lookup. Although this approach proved highly robust against tempo changes, it showed sensitivity towards moderate speed changes.

Dupraz and Gaël Richard [5] introduced a system that used landmarks to deal with moderate speed changes ranging from $\pm 5\%$. They had to pre-process exhaustively to find common pitch offsets between query fingerprints and reference databases. Whenever a constant pitch offset is detected, it can help scale the query.

Anguera et al. [6] described a method which compares the average energies of regions in the spectrogram using a mask designed by them. This approach made their solution more robust under different situations.

Ramona and Peeters [7] developed an algorithm based on double-nested STFTs for estimating the evolution of spectral band energies over time. Instead of computing STFT as the summation of squared amplitudes (equivalent to applying rectangle filters), they computed short-term band energies using cosine filters, thus making it robust against pitch shifting. The method was appropriate for use in large collections

of audio files and was resistant to degradation caused by changes in tempo or shifts in pitch scale, among others.

To increase robustness against speed changes, Ouali et al. [8]. changed quantized spectrogram regions to horizontal and vertical slices, also known as 48-dimensional fingerprints. To achieve this, they first identified all possible matches before conducting additional searches using rescaled versions of the query snippet. However, these exhaustive searches were time-consuming for larger reference collections.

Spectrogram Saliency Maps by Guzman-Zavaleta et al. [9] withstood various signal processing transformations, common temporal desynchronization attacks and real-world noise addition such as coloured noise.

The AFP task was accomplished with exceptional success rates by Zhang et al. and Malekesmaeili and Ward [10, 11, 12]. Their approaches had better resistance against scale distortions than earlier methods used for this purpose. Meanwhile, Six and Leman's method has remained the only technique applicable to large-scale fingerprinting tasks. Nevertheless, it lacked moderate scale distortion robustness, which was its main disadvantage according to them [10, 11, 12].

Son et al. [13]. have proposed a Fundamental Frequency Map (FFMAP) that creates fingerprints and builds hash codes to deal with pitch shifting and time scaling attacks. The similarity of the two audios was quantified by computing the Hamming distance between hash codes. However, this method only worked well on certain types of songs and attacks; it failed in real-world situations where speech or other noise overlays the music.

When we look at all these different ideas, we can see how much audio fingerprinting has grown from what Haitsma and Kalker [3, 2] originally came up with. They were trying for something more durable in different scenarios – but still worked quickly so it could be used widely too!

2.1.3 AFP from Local Peaks

Originally, the early audio fingerprinting relied on peaks in the spectrum to create unique identifiers for sound clips. Currently, these methods are no longer state-of-the-art but still serve as key tools in this field. There were three main methods used:

- **Pairs of peaks:** Developed by Shazam, this method hashes a combination of time-frequency peak pairs. The attributes must be translated as invariant, time-localized, noise-robust, and diverse enough.
- **Triples of peaks:** This method extends the pair's approach, which uses groups of three local maxima from the Constant-Q transform (CQT). It should be able to handle pitch and time-scale changes, including time ratios and frequency differences in the fingerprints.
- **Quads of peaks:** Four spectral peaks are grouped in this technique, which gives it a hash that can stretch over time but fails with GSM compression due to its high resource consumption, even though it outperforms other AFP algorithms.

Another method based on Constant-Q Transform instead of STFT appeared promising under real-world conditions; however, similarly generated hashes posed problems during the retrieval phase.

Though these methods are old, they give us basic knowledge about AFP systems using spectral peaks. Their importance remains very high at industrial-level applications, too. Therefore, one would say that evolution shows how much people strive for better performance while considering different factors like robustness against various attacks or the amount of resources consumed by the algorithm during operation on audio signals being identified.

Another peak-based audio identification method is constellation mapping. The new technique strengthens the queue of audio signal analysis by emphasizing peaks in

time and frequency, thereby improving identification. Ellis [14] presents the Constellation Map Method to speed up music recognition and improve speech processing.

2.1.4 AFP from NN

Audio fingerprinting made significant advancements since its first inception, with another important milestone being the use of neural networks. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), well-known architectures for detecting patterns beyond human capability, have markedly revolutionized audio signal processing. Kim, Park and Lee conducted research [15] where they proved lots of effectiveness in terms of maintenance cost and improvements in accuracy with sound recognition systems based on CNNs. This research gives an outlook on neural networks in this field.

In audio signal processing, CNNs and RNNs are commonly chosen because their architectures were designed for different problems — convolutional layers in case of spatial or temporal patterns (processing), which suit them well when image recognition tasks come into play. They work great in classifying/segmenting audios because when looking at a part of the signal, which we call local features (very useful for frequency components or temporal relations between sounds), CNNs can extract more information from them than other methods.

In summary, CNNs are designed to learn local patterns and characteristics, while RNNs could better model sequential data and capture long-term dependencies in audio sequences. Each has its benefits for processing various parts of neural network sound, which can be used in several ways here.

2.2 NN in music identification

Neural networks have become all the rage in recent years, and they are being used for everything from Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), which are now fundamentally changing music identification. Spatial and Temporal Characteristics in Audio Signals—These architectures do very well for

high-level abstractions when dealing with audio signals. Since 2017, CNN has been widely used to extract spatial and temporal features from audio signals. To validate that CNNs are capable of identifying the most familiar musical instruments in polyphonic music, Han et al. (2017) [16] performed a milestone study demonstrating also how deep convolutional structures make well-fitted networks for searching complex patterns from audio data and providing essential components when implementing any song identification system on these systems.

This innovation happened in 2017 when continuous low-power music recognition systems were created. For example, Agüera y Arcas et al. (2017) [17] developed a system called “Now Playing” at Google Research. It works only on a mobile device and includes a neural network-based fingerprinter and a music detector for passive identification of songs with minimal battery drain. Fingerprinters create small yet distinct fingerprints from short audio pieces, while music detectors save energy by activating them only if any sign of music is played nearby. What differentiates the Now-playing project from others is their use of neural networks trained using a semi-hard triplet loss function. This algorithm initially came from face recognition technology. In their setup, they recognised songs from the 44-hour audio database, thus proving how applicable neural networks can be in real-life music detection scenarios.

Transitioning to 2018, AFP took a big step forward in representation learning with contrasting. Contrastive Predictive Coding (CPC), introduced by Oord, Li and Vinyals (2018), enables useful audio representations to be developed through positive-negative pair differentiation. It has proved very helpful in tasks where robust audio fingerprints are needed.

In the same year, multi-sample contrastive learning was introduced to further improve the discriminative power of learned representations. Khosla et al. (2020) [18] advanced this field by extending contrastive learning techniques, demonstrating improved performance in various tasks.

Recently, the paper "Simultaneously Learning Robust Audio Embeddings and Bal-

anced Hash Codes for Query-by-Example" [19] proposed a new solution to QbE tasks in audio retrieval. It is suggested that they be trained jointly with their audio embeddings to generate the binary hash codes for both at once to keep the robust and balanced content of those hashings. This approach, in general, significantly improves retrieval performance, with effectiveness and speed relatively high for robustness against noise or variations occurring within the audio data.

The development of audio fingerprinting methods has undergone a paradigm shift with the advent of self-supervised learning models such as SAMAF [20] or the Self-Supervised Autoencoder Model for Audio Fingerprinting. Using a self-taught autoencoder model, this technique ensures high precision in identifying sounds. It generates robust music fingerprints through self-supervision and leverages them for effective and efficient music recognition. Another framework proposed in 2020 shows how much can be achieved within audio fingerprinting through self-supervised learning while also solving retrieval tasks with high specificity.

Finally, this paper, "Neural Audio Fingerprint for High-Specific Audio Retrieval Based on Contrastive Learning", [21] builds upon a foundation to investigate how contrastive learning may be used in audio fingerprinting. In the experiment, they propose a neural network audio fingerprint method that produces strong LogMel Spectrogram-based robust and discriminative audio fingerprints using convolutional networks and L2 projection Layers through contrastive learning, significantly improving retrieval performance.

2.3 AFP datasets

Despite its widespread application, the field of AFP has yet to mature and improve by using standard public datasets, as many works proposing models for this task have exploited some private data. However, we provide them in detail below.

We identified 22 datasets from the literature used in AFP. After examining what the data is composed of, many are grounded on the same idea, where we have a set of tracks (private) considered references and another [query] referring to transformed

/ degraded versions from some references. These are suitable datasets for pushing the limits of decompositional robustness to artefacts like pitch shift or time scale. However, these do not meet the requirements of a live-action, realistic audiovisual production because of how the music will be in the background. At the same time, there are dialogues and several different kinds of natural noises.

Six public datasets have been used for Audio Fingerprinting, and they are listed in Table 1. There are only seven datasets because publishing copyrighted music legally is challenging. In what follows, we give a short description of these mentioned datasets:

MagnaTagATune¹ dataset contains 25,863 music clips of 29 seconds each from 5,223 songs by 230 artists. Various music genres are represented: Rock, Pop, Jazz, Electronic, New Age, and Classical. Each audio clip is represented by a vector of binary annotations of 188 tags. These annotations were created by humans using the two-player online game "TagATune".

TRECVID² is an event where organisations with an interest in the field of Information Retrieval coordinate to perform a series of experiments using the same data. Until 2011, there was a Content-Based Copy Detection (CCD) task where the dataset created for it (12,000 videos) could be adapted to Audio Fingerprinting, although its use for this task has been very limited.

Panako³ Joren Six and Marc Leman created in 2014 Panako, an audio fingerprinting system, which they presented at ISMIR. In addition, they published a dataset of 30,000 references.

Mixotic⁴ contains 10 DJ sessions playing 723 references sourced from Jamendo⁵. TRECVID contains about 12,000 files extracted from the Internet Archive ⁶ and released under a Creative Commons license.

¹<https://mirg.city.ac.uk/codeapps/the-magnatagatune-dataset>

²<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2629531>

³<https://0110.be/releases/Panako/Panako-1.4/readme.html>

⁴<http://www.cp.jku.at/datasets/fingerprinting/>

⁵<https://www.jamendo.com/>

⁶<https://archive.org/>

Neural Audio FP⁷ uses a selection of data from the Free Music Archive (FMA⁸). It is a dataset widely used in various MIR tasks. It contains 106,574 songs, and although it is not oriented toward audio fingerprinting, it could be used to create a dataset with BMAT's recordings. The same goes for MagnaTagATune (MTAT), which contains 25,863 music clips from 5,223 references, and MTG-Jamendo, which contains 55,000 from Jamendo.

BAF[22]⁹ is a dataset developed by BMAT in collaboration with the Music Technology Group of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra and Epidemic Sound within the framework of the NextCore project (RTC2019-007248-7). It contains 74 hours of production music from the Epidemic Sound Library and 57 hours of audio from television broadcast recordings.

We can improve AFP algorithms in several ways, so it is hard to say which is the best. What AFP algorithm to use may be determined by specific application needs such as speed, robustness or energy consumption. Therefore, current investigations continue to expand the limits of what can be achieved, thus ensuring vibrancy and continuous growth within this study area.

⁷<https://mimbres.github.io/neural-audio-fp/>

⁸<https://github.com/mdeff/fma>

⁹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6868083>

Chapter 3

CueSet: A Dataset for Testing

The following section will show how I created a new dataset to investigate background music fingerprinting. It consists of the entire journey, from detecting a problem to selecting audio files and annotating them.

Therefore, CueSet was developed to provide a more specific basis for evaluating neural networks and addressing the complexities of identifying background music fingerprints in these video streaming services. This comprehensive approach aims to bridge the gap between current challenges and specific solutions for this context, contributing to advancing knowledge in this area.

3.1 Why this dataset

These data challenges require new, bespoke datasets to assess audio fingerprinting systems in the Video-on-demand (VoD) scenario for which CueSet is needed. Although prior benchmarks like BAF [22] have conducted valuable work, they may need to be more comprehensive to account for this inherent complexity and variance within VoD acquisitions. There are concerns about the generalizability as VoD is quite a different beast in content presentation and delivery than traditional broadcasting.

CueSet addresses these challenges by closely replicating the typical conditions found

in VoD services, such as those operated by BMAT. VoD content is known for its complex audio backgrounds, which include background music, spoken dialogue, and sound effects that often overlap with the featured foregrounded elements. CueSet integrates audio settings to simulate real production conditions, including low-volume background music and overlaying sound layers.

The dataset maintains this stance regarding companies like BMAT, which require a true reflection of what the audio conditions will be in reality and have high standards for sensitivity and reliability from their service provision. Using CueSets for testing enables the measurement on a more realistic and reliable ground and assures that fingerprinting systems will be accurate in execution within depending on VoD, rendering all into higher quality music identification processes down the production line.

3.2 Dataset Requirements

3.2.1 Cue-Sheets and Fingerprinting Analysis

To create the CueSet dataset, which was built using previous matches identified by BMAT’s audio fingerprinting technology. These early games played a good jumping-off point, mainly when emerging background music. Recognising the difficulty of getting reliable results for background music with inherently low saliency, we argued that these initial matches are guaranteed to fail whenever even mildly obscured by other elements.

In background music environments, a common problem with these initial matches is what comes to be known as *split matches* as seen on the figure 1. This means that a single music track is broken into several bits because the volume is low or there is a superimposition of sounds, and so on—also fragmented, causing wrong identifications. These errors render the model inaccurate in reliably predicting background music and stress the importance of correct maintenance.

Figure 1: Illustrative picture of the split-matches problem

We got freelancers to manually review and correct these split matches very diligently. These made the background music very hard to track (and additionally prone to many splitting mistakes), and focusing on cases such as this was able to help us purify our dataset. This elaborate correction process is why we have a diverse number of complex audio samples in CueSet — which, therefore, enormously benefit the evaluation for testing and improving fingerprinting algorithms, especially friend-and-foe scenarios with subdued background music.

The stringent selection of complex content and matches that had been shuffled based on their background enabled us to arrive at a robust dataset with many challenges. Completing this dataset of various challenging audio is an essential advance in the field, making it useful for many other applications that involve indexing or matching musical content. It shows that even relatively small improvements in background music fingerprinting are possible without resorting to crazy levels of feature selec-

tion/filter/scrubbing on intermediate audio representations, so it should be a valuable resource for algorithm testing and tuning benchmarks where the background is gentle enough to fade into overall silence.

In BMAT's day-to-day operations, this is one of the most frequent cases in identifying music in audiovisual productions and generating cue sheets. Multiple consecutive identifications of the same reference probably indicate that the audio material presents difficulties for the algorithm. For this reason, detecting several successive matches of the same reference suggests that the audio material presents challenges for the algorithm.

3.2.2 Additional Considerations

To begin with, the importance of data privacy is highlighted. This suggests that security measures must be taken to ensure the confidentiality of customer information. Secondly, it is important to include diversity in the content of a dataset. This means various audio-visual materials should be considered based on genres, languages and origins. Finally, the relevance of dataset size is mentioned. It should not be very big since such sets are used as an initial stage while training and/or validating a fingerprinting model for robustness and generalization purposes.

3.3 CueSet compilation process

3.3.1 Access to Private Cue-sheets

There are two things to consider. The first is about data protection and confidentiality, which means that access control must be strict, and security measures must be taken. Secondly, cue sheets will be retrieved by querying the company's internal database alone, where only authorized persons can access them. Another thing is that before using cue sheets for research purposes, all personal details shall be stripped off through anonymization to guarantee the privacy of information.

3.3.2 Search and Compilation Methodology

The following parameters have been taken as selection criteria for obtaining cue sheets. Initially, the duration range of the background music segments is considered by selecting those that fall within the limits defined in a certain range. Furthermore, it has been decided not to discriminate by musical genre, thus ensuring an equitable inclusion of all genres in the dataset. Additionally, the cue sheets were selected from diverse sources and channels. To ensure a wide range of audiovisual content, the dataset has been curated with a focus on data obtained from the BMAT's CueD tool database. Finally, a programmatic search is carried out to identify those audiovisual files in which cues with the exact reference identification are detected at least thrice.

This repetition suggests the possibility of an error in the algorithm, which would indicate the presence of a single reference instead of three, as mentioned previously.

3.3.3 Methodology for Sample Selection

The following procedure shows the phases for obtaining said samples. Raw information is extracted from each client database based on a specific criterion:

- The record contains a file that is not empty.
- That it is within a duration range defined by the user.

And we want the response to only give us certain fields from the collection:

- The identification of the record.
- The file information to be able to download it if it meets the requirements.
- The file information to be able to download it if it meets the requirements.
- The total duration in seconds.
- The cue-sheets field, which is the most necessary to be able to apply the filtering criteria on it.
- The title or name of the audiovisual program in question, since, as a general rule, it contains the file extension

As a search strategy, as seen on 2 *has_consecutive_reference_ids* is the one that looks for the same *reference_id* appearing consecutively a specific number of times in a list of cues (tracks).

These are the function arguments:

cues: The list to be analysed. Every track here is a dictionary, and it must have a key called *cue_identifiers* whose value is also a dictionary containing another key named *reference_id*.

times: This represents the required number of consecutive appearances of the same *reference_id* for it to be treated as matching.

The process of this function is such that it counts tracks having equal successive occurrences of *reference_ids* while scanning through them. If there happens to be any sequence where an identical reference appears ‘times’ several times successively according to what was stated in the time’s argument, it prints those tracks out and gives back *reference_id* together with tracks forming that sequence.

If none of these sequences meets its requirements, then None will be returned by this function.

```
function has_consecutive_reference_ids(cues, times=3):
    initialize current_id, count, cues_list
    for cue in cues:
        get reference_id from cue
        if reference_id != current_id:
            update current_id, reset count, clear cues_list
        increment count, add cue to cues_list
        if count == times:
            return reference_id and cues_list
    return None and None
```

Figure 2: pseudo code for the sample finding strategy

For example, having the following list of tracks, in a very simplified way:

The *has_consecutive_ids* function will return:

Because *reference_id* "A" appears thrice in the last cues.

Once the cues have been obtained, I calculate each segment’s precise start and end times using a specific criterion.

```
cues = [  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "B"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
]
```

Figure 3: Example data for testing

```
"A", [  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
  {"cue_identifiers": {"reference_id": "A"}},  
]
```

Figure 4: Example of needed result

For this, I have created a class that calculates the start and end times for a set of cues (tracks) given a total duration and an arbitrary offset in seconds.

The method takes three arguments:

- **cues**: a list of tracks, each track being a dictionary containing at least the keys *relative_start_time* and *duration*.
- **duration**: the total duration of the audio or video file
- **offset**: an offset subtracted from the start time of the first track and added to the end time of the last track.

This calculates the start time as the relative start time of the first track minus the offset and the end time as the relative start time of the third track plus its duration plus the offset.

If the calculated start time is less than 0, it is adjusted to 0. If the calculated end time exceeds the total duration, it is adjusted to the total duration. If the difference

between the end and start times is less than 10 seconds or greater than 20 minutes, it returns 'None,' and we discard the file in question.

Finally, the method returns a dictionary with the calculated start and end times.

Figure 5: Cue timing block diagram

3.4 Audio and Video Pre-processing

Processing the audio files from the previous step takes an input and output directory as arguments during initialization. It then iterates through all files in the input directory, processes the audio files (specifically *.aac* files) with the help of the well-known Python library *Librosa*, downsamples them to a sampling rate of 8,000 Hz, converts them to a single mono channel, and saves them as *.wav* files in the output directory. If an audio file is processed successfully, the original file is deleted. The class also records the files that were successfully processed and those that failed. At the end of processing, it prints the number of successfully processed files and those that failed to process. The processed files should be in the output folder. Some audio may be lost during this process because the file may be corrupted.

3.5 Dataset Annotation

The code provided in the previous section does not cover the annotation of the dataset, which involves the identification and labelling of the audio segments with their corresponding fingerprints. This has been addressed by detailing strategies to ensure the quality and reliability of the labels and has been carried out with the help of the annotation tool developed by BMAT's R&D team, illustrated on 6.

Figure 6: Annotation tool

The analyzed dataset contains a total of 325 correct matches, which together amount

to a total duration of 13,361 seconds, with an average of 41 seconds per match. However, during the annotation process, I identified numerous false positives, which have been marked as such by the freelancer in charge. Specifically, 379 false positives were recorded, totalling 1,560 seconds and an average of 4 seconds per false positive. These errors originated mainly due to sound effects shared between samples, which, although they do not technically affect the match, are irrelevant from a business point of view.

Despite the challenges posed by sound effects in the dataset, they have been included in the annotations for possible use in future evaluations. This presence of sound effects not only hinders the identification of background music but also complicates the removal of non-musical false positives by a standard audio fingerprinting system, confirming the challenging nature of the dataset.

Furthermore, the annotations in the dataset distinguish between false and true positives. In the case of false positives, three main categories are identified: *fp_sample*, which refers to shared non-musical samples; *fp_percussion*, which indicates typical percussion samples, often taken from standard libraries; and *fp_music*, which means musical samples shared between two different songs. On the other hand, true positives are also subdivided into two types: *tp_exact*, when the reference exactly matches what is heard in the query, and *tp_version*, when the reference is slightly different, for example, with the addition or removal of some instrument, although it is still clearly the same musical reference. Additionally, *doubtful* annotations were included, indicating that the annotator could not determine whether the match was correct.

Once annotated, this dataset provides a wide range of true and false matches and detailed annotations that allow for evaluating different aspects and types of matches for their analysis and continuous improvement.

Chapter 4

Methodology

In this section, I try to improve the neural network-based audio fingerprinting system, Neural Audio FP library [21]. In the following subsections, I will delve into its core concepts, what augmentations it is using, and the experiments I have performed using different data-augmentation approaches with the help of the "*audiomentations*" library ¹ as well as extra code modifications to match our use case for background music identification.

4.1 Core Concepts of Neural Audio Fp

Neural Audio Fp is an advanced audio fingerprinting package built on neural networking. It has been designed to create robust, unique audio fingerprints. The document uses contrastive learning to describe a high-specificity neural audio fingerprinter for sequence search performance. It investigates the impact of the batch size, fingerprint dimension, query length and other factors on search accuracy and performance.

Some of the main highlights are the results of experiments that indicate how batch size, fingerprint dimension, and query length affect search accuracy and efficiency. The proposed method performs better than the semi-hard triplet approach by im-

¹<https://iver56.github.io/audiomentations/>

proving exact match performance. Additionally, it explores transfer learning to other tasks, such as audio genre classification in which learned embeddings may be interpreted.

A working audio fingerprinting system has to meet various vital requirements. It must differ from many other fingerprints, so it needs high discriminability. Robustness is essential, as different acoustic distortions can occur during transmission-storage, or audio FX or speech can come mixed with the audio, necessitating robust systems to recover accurately. Finally, efficiency is essential compared to large-scale databases because they want a quick response time in the content identification process.

4.2 Contrastive Learning Framework

The contrastive learning framework used in Neural Audio Fp derives from the segment-level search objective. Each update in training involves a batch with pseudo labels, randomly selected original samples called *anchors*, and their augmented *replicas* to simulate degrading effects on original audio signals. This framework aims to enhance the discriminability and robustness of the audio fingerprinting system for high-specific audio retrieval.

Developing an audio fingerprint system facilitating high-specificity retrieval at scale is one of the main challenges in this paper, as existing systems might require additional post-processes for specific segment retrieval purposes within an extensive database. They introduce a new neural audio fingerprinting framework that consists of, on the one hand, a neural network trained to generate compact and discriminative fingerprints from short audio excerpts in an unsupervised fashion, using contrastive learning as the optimization criterion which ensures similar input fragments have learned equal representations while forcing dissimilar ones apart; and on the other hand, provides fast retrieval based on similarity between fingerprints by making use of Maximum Inner Product Search (MIPS).

The proposed fingerprint generation model consists of the following:

- **Convolutional Network Layer:** They extract local temporal features from the audio waveform, capturing key patterns within the audio data.
- **Pooling Layers:** Pooling layers downscale the size of inputs to manage computational complexity and strengthen model Invariance.
- **Fully Connected Layers:** The features are projected into a low-dimensional embedding space to generate audio fingerprints.

Figure 7: Neural Audio FP layers extracted from [21]

The model is trained using a contrastive loss function where fingerprints corresponding to the same audio segment (with different augmentation) are encouraged to come closer in embedding space and those belonging to various segments far.

To efficiently retrieve the fingerprints, two MIPS algorithms have been investigated using different indexing mechanisms: Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH), a probabilistic method hashing similar features to be in the same buckets, and Product Quantization (PQ), an alternative vector quantized technique that converts feature vectors into compact representations for fast distance computation. Together with the system proposed, these algorithms can guarantee efficient and accurate retrieval from very large-scale audio databases.

4.3 Data Augmentations

The process used by the authors of this study involves several augmentation techniques highly relevant to the field of audio signal processing and machine learning. These techniques mimic audio anomalies in the real world and bolster the model’s robustness. They include the training process:

- **Modulation of Time Offset:** The authors have considered positive examples as 1-second audio clips with an offset of up to ± 200 ms to simulate possible discrepancies in real-world search scenarios. To achieve this, they sample 1.2 seconds worth of sound and choose the original section along with the duplicate section randomly based on where it starts.
- **Background Mixing:** Noise is randomly chosen within the SNR range $[0, 10]$ dB and added into the audio to represent actual noise conditions. The noise dataset includes 4.3 hours from part of AudioSet [23] and another 2.3 hours recorded by the authors that has pub/ cafe noise. For AudioSet, filtering was done such that subways, metros or other underground places were included, but music-related tags were excluded. Both datasets have been divided into training set (80%) and test set (20%).
- **Impulse Response(IR) Filters:** Authors take microphone impulse responses (MIRs) and room impulse responses (RIRs) as public datasets, which are meant for simulating different spatial environments together with microphones, respectively, using convolution operations in sequence.
- **Cutout and Spec-Augment:** Once log-power Mel-spectrogram features have been extracted from audio data, Cutout/Audio-spec [24] robustness is applied during the augmentation stage, where random masks are put on parts of spectrograms. In contrast with other augmentation forms, a batch-wise random mask will be spread evenly across all examples within a batch, including the original segment. The size, as well as position for each rectangular/vertical/horizontal mask, is selected at random so that it can range between 1/10

to 1/2 length for every time/frequency axis

4.4 Improvements

The main idea of this work is to develop on top of the Neural Audio Fp framework. All of them are designed to make the system more reliable and precise. The significant enhancements are as follows:

- **Enhanced Data Augmentations:** I included several audio augmentations to improve generalization and robustness. This gives you a range of tools to simulate real-world scenarios and distortions that might be applied to the audio.
- **Specific Speech Mixing:** The speech mixing processing was tweaked so that voice or dialogue is upfront with background music to keep it more relevant, especially when we have dialogue scenes over music. We also include synthetic dialogue for broadcasting and multimedia scenarios when primary speech audio has long gaps.

4.4.1 Proposed augmentations

In order to make the model generalize better, I applied a few different audio augmentations using *audiomentations* Python package. Using this package, we can simulate various real-life scenarios and distortions that audio might encounter, allowing the model to be more robust at handling different or noisy environments. These augmentations were chosen following a qualitative evaluation of the cueSet dataset to ensure their relevance and usefulness.

- **AddGaussianNoise** was used to introduce Gaussian noise to the audio signals, simulating random background noise. This helps the model become robust to different noise levels encountered in real-world scenarios. The noise was added with a minimum amplitude of 0.0005–0.001 and a maximum amplitude of 0.005–0.01.

- **AddBackgroundNoise** added background noises to the audio, reflecting realistic environmental conditions. The noise sources included subsets of AudioSet and recordings from public places like pubs and cafes. This augmentation aimed to mimic situations where background noise is present. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was randomly chosen between 30, 35, or 40 dB as the minimum and 45, 50, or 55 dB as the maximum, with the noise RMS being relative.
- **PitchShift** was employed to modify the pitch of the audio by shifting it up or down by several semitones. It helps the model recognize audio content slightly altered in pitch, simulating different recording conditions or playback speeds. The pitch was shifted by a minimum of -2 to -1 semitones or a maximum of 1 to 2 semitones.
- **HighPassFilter** and **LowPassFilter** were applied to filter out low and high frequencies, respectively. These augmentations simulate the effects of various recording and playback devices, which may have different frequency response characteristics. For the HighPassFilter, the minimum cutoff frequency ranged from 50 to 150 Hz, and the maximum cutoff frequency ranged from 200 to 300 Hz. The minimum rolloff was set between 6, 12, and 18 dB. The LowPassFilter had a minimum cutoff frequency between 15,000 and 17,000 Hz and a maximum cutoff frequency between 18,000 and 19,000 Hz, with the same rolloff values as the HighPassFilter.
- **BandPassFilter** was used to isolate specific frequency bands, particularly those relevant to speech. It helps train the model to focus on the most informative parts of the audio signal. The bandpass filter values for center frequency and bandwidth were set to isolate frequencies vital to speech recognition, ensuring that the model concentrated on the most informative components of the signal.
- **Gain** adjustment was used to increase or decrease the audio volume randomly. It helps the model become robust to variations in recording levels and playback

volumes. The minimum gain was set between -12 and -6 dB, and the maximum gain ranged from 1 to 6 dB.

- **GainTransition** was introduced to simulate gradual changes in gain over time, reflecting real-world scenarios where the audio volume might increase or decrease smoothly. It helps the model adapt to dynamic audio environments. The duration of the gain transition was defined as a fraction, with a minimum duration of 0.2 to 0.4 seconds and a maximum duration of 0.5 to 0.6 seconds. The gain values ranged from -6 to -2 dB on the lower end and 2 to 6 dB on the upper end.
- **LoudnessNormalization** was applied to standardize the perceived loudness of audio segments. It ensures that the loudness of the audio does not bias the model and allows it to focus on the content. Loudness was normalized within a specific range to create consistency across samples.
- **Normalization** was used to adjust the audio signal to a standard level, ensuring consistency across different samples and making the model robust to variations in recording quality. This was done with a controlled probability to avoid over-normalizing the audio.
- **Limiter** was applied to prevent the audio signal from exceeding a certain threshold, simulating the effect of audio compression and preventing distortion. The limiter threshold was set between -1 and 0 dB.

They all have a probability of one, which means that when called, it is applied every time.

These augmentations collectively strengthen the model to deal with a variety of real-world audio conditions, ultimately enhancing its generalization and robustness.

To include these augmentations during the training, I created an **augmentor pipeline factory**. This would let me take a staged approach to implementing data augmentation. This class creates an "augmentor" for each epoch by sampling from audio

augmentations with random parameters as we have set above. The design of the approach will lead to more augmentation, variety, and complexity as we move ahead with epochs.

When compared with the basic augmentation, the incremental method introduces a greater number of augmentations by training a single model in stages. This method should significantly enhance the generalization and robustness of our model. Therefore, the 'augmentor' pipeline factory, a crucial component in preparing training data, plays a key role in ensuring the model can effectively learn from both clean and dirty audio samples during training.

4.4.2 Speech Mixing

My changes to the audio processing pipeline are substantial, especially for our edge case of having spoken content in front and music further away. In particular, fine-tuning the voice-priority mixing algorithm is an essential process. The only drawback to this method is that the audio fingerprints generated are more specific about situations in which accurate and precise background music identification needs to be performed. By highlighting the voice signals, even with pronounced speeches or dialogue, we were able to make the system better learn how music should be distinguished and recognised.

It was the speech at first, but not how I thought. It may have been in the background. For my use case, I made it more towards voice/dialogue in the foreground and music background using a mixing feature. A crucial feature of the system is that it can be adapted to any use case. On top of that, I included a unique speech mix to simulate dialogue, but only if there are gaps in the original speech audio sample. With the help of this adjustment, our audio fingerprints will be more precise when voice-over music is played (e.g., broadcast or multimedia content).

To achieve the dialogue feature, I used a subset of LibriSpeech [25], a freely available dataset featuring approximately 1,000 hours of clean, read English speech derived from audiobooks, which is a cornerstone resource for automatic speech recognition

(ASR) research and development. It offers diverse training, development, and testing sets, focusing on clean speech segments. While primarily employed for ASR model training and benchmarking, its well-segmented and aligned nature makes it suitable for various speech-related tasks. Although not explicitly designed for dialogue, the clean speech data within LibriSpeech is valuable for training dialogue system components requiring high-quality speech.

Furthermore, I adjusted the background music to be less prominent, simulating real-world scenarios where background music is often subtle. This adjustment ensures that the system can still accurately identify and isolate the background music, even when it is mixed with more dominant voice signals. By reducing the prominence of the background music, the system is challenged to recognize and generate accurate audio fingerprints for the music, which is critical for effective background music identification in video-on-demand content. This approach enhances the system's ability to detect and identify background music in more realistic, mixed audio environments.

4.5 Training

This training process included one-second segments, which permitted the use of dialogue. All the above setup was trained and validated with a batch size of 320, and we use LAMB [26] as an optimizer to save time for tuning the learning rate. This model had 16,897,920 parameters or about 64.46 MB of memory, which was huge at the time. Training took around two days per experiment mainly because the augmentations run on the CPU much slower than GPU-based augmentation. Although GPU augmentations could accelerate the process, they were less available and thus not utilized in this instance.

The following figure of pseudo-code gives an idea about the training process:

1. Defined the configuration parameters and variables.
2. Initialized the encoder and projection layer.
3. **Created a custom augmentor pipeline factory.**
4. Training loop that:
 - (a) **Applies speech or dialogue in the foreground.**
 - (b) **Computes the representations for original and augmented samples through the custom augmentor.**
 - (c) Concatenates these representations.
 - (d) Computes the pairwise similarity matrix.
 - (e) Calculates the loss.
 - (f) Performs backpropagation and optimization.

Figure 8: Pseudo-code additions in bold of the training pipeline

4.5.1 Experiments

I ran a series of experiments on the audio-fingerprinting model with different augmentation strategies, each executed under its own experiment name.

I experimented with an initial incremental version in the *06_19_train_aalbas* but had to stop this after noticing a significant growth in training and validation losses. In the *06_20_train_aalbas* experiment, I tried again with a more conservative incremental approach and slight augmentations. Training and validation loss was (1.9894, 3.7236) seconds.

For the experiment *06_23_train_aalbas*, I used a non-incremental strategy, seeing all augmentations from the beginning. This gave me a training loss of 1.69% and a validation loss of 5.49 %. Within the *06_28_train_aalbasonlyspeech* experiment, I was not incrementally augmenting and focusing on only speech — both led to another significant improvement in training/validation metrics.

The experiment *06_30_train* simulated a new, improved incremental strategy, which led to significant improvements, especially in validation loss. Then, I knew that my different style was working.

Nevertheless, with the *07_03_train_aalbas_noaugdialog* experiment, which ruled out incremental augmentations and dialogue features, I noticed this model experienced early convergence as training will stop due to reaching my desired number of epochs.

This should illustrate that not all augmentation strategies work and the necessity to perform hyper-parameter tuning when it comes to data augmentations to achieve optimal model performance.

All experiments, in a total of 6, are reproducible with this repository’s configuration and commit history.².

4.6 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of the newly trained models. I used several key metrics, aligning with the methodologies suggested in the BAF paper [22]. Specifically, I evaluated depending on the following metrics:

- **Percentage of Identified Seconds:** This metric measures the proportion of correctly identified seconds of audio compared to the total duration of the audio reference. It provides an overall sense of the system’s ability to recognize and accurately match audio segments over time.
- **Precision:** Precision is the ratio of true positive matches to the sum of true positives and false positives. It indicates the system’s accuracy in identifying correct matches without mistakenly identifying non-matching segments as matches.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

- **Recall:** Recall is the ratio of true positive matches to the sum of true positives and false negatives. This metric measures the system’s ability to correctly

²https://github.com/sonoalex/neuralfp/tree/alex_main

identify all relevant matches from the audio reference.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

- **F1-Score:** The F1-Score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It provides a single metric that balances the system's precision and recall, offering a comprehensive view of its performance.

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

- **Precision-Recall curve:** It is a graphical representation used to evaluate the performance of a binary classifier. It plots precision (the proportion of true positive predictions among all positive predictions) against recall (the proportion of true positive predictions among all actual positive instances) at various threshold settings. The curve provides insight into the trade-off between precision and recall for different thresholds: a high precision indicates a low false positive rate, while a high recall indicates a low false negative rate.
 - **AUC (Area Under the Curve):** The area under the curve (AUC) was also calculated to quantify the overall ability of the system to discriminate between positive and negative matches. An AUC value closer to 1 indicates a higher performance level.

Chapter 5

Results

In this section, I present the results on the proposed CueSet dataset of the public Neural Audio Fp model (baseline) and the three main experiments conducted. The rest of the experiments presented in 4.5.1 can be treated as preliminary experiments that have not been reported in this thesis.

5.1 Baseline Model Results

The baseline results presented in table 1 are computed in the public model *640_lamb* of neural audio fingerprinting [21] on the CueSet dataset. The CueSet, developed to match the real-world conditions of audio-only description for video-on-demand (VoD) content, was a test bench to determine how well prototype models could detect musical background within complex VoD-like programme material. Looking into true positives (TPs), false positives (FPs), and false negatives (FNs), I can obtain metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score. Hence, it offers a detailed view of the model's current capabilities and the areas that still need improvement.

Here are the detailed results:

- **True Positives (TPs):** The model correctly identified 3,860.42 seconds of background music.

- **False Positives (FPs):** The model incorrectly identified 3,119.08 seconds as background music when it was not present. This includes, on the one hand, 2,988 seconds as overlength of *False Positives*, where the model incorrectly extended the detection of background music beyond its actual duration, and on the other hand, 131.08 seconds, marked as *False positives Other* due to other types of errors
- **False Negatives (FNs):** The model missed to identify 9,501.25 seconds of background music that was actually present.

Based on these values, the following metrics were calculated according to the BAF [22] evaluation metrics:

- **Precision:** was 0.553 (55.31%), as the proportion of correctly identified background music seconds out of all identified.
- **Recall:** was 0.289 (28.89%), as the proportion of actual background music seconds correctly identified.
- **F1-score:** which balances precision and recall, was 0.380 (37.96%)

These results indicate that although the baseline model performed well in terms of precision, almost invariably hitting background music and reducing false positives due to this, its recall value was low, indicating that it missed many instances of background music. The F1-Score suggests that a better precision/recall trade-off must be made to improve the model’s ability to detect background music correctly.

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	TP’s	FPs	FNs
Baseline	0.553	0.289	0.380	3860.4	3119.2	9501.3

Table 1: Results for the current baseline.

5.2 Experiment Results

In this section, I present the results of the three main experiments reported in table 2 on background music identification using various audio data and augmentation configurations. From the six experiments I conducted, I finally chose the three more relevant ones: (1) using augmentations from the beginning, (2) incorporating only speech data mixed with dialogue, and (3) adding augmentations incrementally to the speech data and the background music. Below, I detail each experiment's results and discuss potential improvements.

For the current findings, I used a unique matching system based on Neural Audio Fp to monitor, as proposed in the BAF paper [22]. The matching system detects and matches audio fingerprints through its capabilities. The Neural Audio Fp approach to generating neural network-based fingerprints offers high discriminability while ensuring efficiency.

This system uses a matching threshold that filters out all matches whose similarity score is below 0.65, as recommended by the BAF publication, where only specific high-confidence matches are considered, thus reducing false positives while increasing the reliability of the process. Furthermore, if a match exists between reference intervals, those above 65% should also be merged, creating more substantial outcomes regarding accuracy during matching. However, it should be noted that the lightweight nature coupled with non-scalability makes this algorithm challenging to deal with efficiently when dealing with large datasets.

We are committed to computing precision-recall curves to enhance performance further and address scalability concerns. This will enable us to identify thresholds better suited to our system and significantly improve its accuracy and efficiency. A strict yet flexible threshold combined with these two approaches leads to high precision-recall for fast, accurate retrieval of audio segments using this matching system. In other words, advanced neural network techniques should be paired with specialized peak detection algorithms, resulting in better performance in tasks related to audio fingerprinting.

Experiment	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	TP's	FPs	FNs
Baseline	0.553	0.289	0.380	3860.4	3119.1	9501.3
Augmentations (No Incr)	0.703	0.434	0.537	5800.8	2448.7	7560.9
Only Speech/Dialog	0.830	0.572	0.677	7642.6	1563.9	5719.1
Speech with Augmentations (Incr)	0.812	0.529	0.641	7074.2	1638.3	6287.5

Table 2: Metric results applied to CueSet.

5.2.1 Experiment 1: Augmentations from the Beginning

In the first experiment, augmentations were applied to the audio data from the beginning without an incremental approach. The results are as follows: false negatives (FNs) totalled 7560.88 seconds, and false positives (FPs) amounted to 2448.71. The model correctly identified 5800.79 seconds true positives (TPs). The overall metrics were an F1-score of 53.7%, a precision of 70.3%, and a recall of 43.4%.

These results show a reasonable precision-recall balance and an average F1 score. However, the model still misses a lot of identifications (false negatives), which means there are many cases where music (positive) is not detected so much. One solution to this problem can be further improving its identification capabilities. Data augmentation works to maintain the same audio features in an unmodified state and statistically improve data diversity with minor corrupts. Further, the model can better generalise for various background music categories and audio contexts by including a more generalised set of diverse song clips in training data.

5.2.2 Experiment 2: Speech Data Only

Introducing the speech and dialogue in the foreground as another augmentation data into the training process significantly improved performance, with precision increasing to 83% and recall increasing to 57%. This is probably because the model can now learn a much more nuanced representational form of audio, which helps it better distinguish between background music and other sounds (dialogue or sound effects). This decrease in FPs demonstrates that the model better distinguishes other items we do not care about from background music.

There are also clear indications of capacity to make the model more robust. This speech data could also fine-tune the graph using different accents, languages, and speaking styles. This way, their model is always flexible and realistic. Leveraging contextually aware approaches and benefitting from recall and audio circumstances also helps improve model performance.

5.2.3 Experiment 3: Speech with Incremental Augmentations

When augmentations are added incrementally to the speech data, there is a slight decrease in recall to 52.9% and F1-score to 64.1%. This suggests that augmentations can't be beneficial. They may also introduce noise or alter the audio to make identification more challenging in this specific scenario. However, precision remains high at 81.2%, indicating that the model is still proficient at correctly identifying background music when detecting it.

As we have a new diversity in data, it needs to be considered with appropriate choice and use of augmentation, not altering the audio features. The effect of augmentations on recall and F1-score was decreased, but the same level of precision was maintained.

5.3 Precision-Recall Curve

The PR visualizes the trade-off between precision (how many identified segments are truly background music) and recall (how much of the actual background music is identified). A curve closer to the top-right corner indicates better performance. "Only Speech" outperforms the other two, especially at higher recall levels, demonstrating its superior ability to identify a more significant portion of background music accurately.

The precision-recall (PR) curve offers insights into the trade-offs between precision and recall at various thresholds:

- **High Precision, Low Recall Region:** At the lower recall values (around 0.2 to 0.4), precision remains high, ranging from approximately 0.89 to 0.79. This indicates that when the system retrieves fewer relevant items (lower recall), it does so with high accuracy (high precision). The thresholds associated with these points are likely higher, ensuring that only the most confident matches are considered, which filters out most false positives but also misses many true positives.
- **Balanced Precision and Recall:** As recall increases from 0.5 to 0.6, precision declines from 0.74 to 0.63. This suggests a trade-off where the system retrieves more relevant items but at the cost of including more false positives. The thresholds here are more balanced, allowing a moderate number of true and false positives.
- **High Recall, Low Precision Region:** At higher recall values (above 0.7), precision drops significantly, falling to around 0.32 by the time recall reaches 0.9. This indicates that when the system aims to retrieve the most relevant items (high recall), it also retrieves many irrelevant items (low precision). The associated thresholds are lower, making the system more permissive and less discriminative, increasing false positives.

- **Threshold Analysis:** The curve provides threshold values at various recall points: 0.89 (at 0.2 recall), 0.84 (at 0.3 recall), 0.79 (at 0.4 recall), 0.74 (at 0.5 recall), 0.68 (at 0.6 recall), 0.63 (at 0.7 recall), 0.58 (at 0.8 recall), and 0.53 (at 0.9 recall). This demonstrates how precision decreases as the threshold is lowered to increase recall. Hence, it is threshold-dependent.

Figure 9: PR curve from the best trained model

5.3.1 Discussion

In the context of BMAT, the precision-recall (PR) curve depicted in figure 9 offers crucial insights into the trade-offs between precision and recall. These trade-offs directly impact the company's effectiveness and the quality of client services. Understanding these trade-offs is essential for aligning the system's performance with BMAT's business objectives, particularly in scenarios where accuracy and reliability are non-negotiable.

High Precision, Low Recall Strategy

In the case of BMAT, maintaining high precision is critical, as incorrect identifications can lead to incorrect royalties distribution. The accuracy of identifying audio content is crucial in music monitoring, as royalties distribution and copyright enforcement are at stake. At lower recall values (around 0.2 to 0.4), the system maintains high precision (between 0.89 and 0.79), meaning that nearly 80% to 90% of the identified matches are correct.

This system is essential in reducing reporting mistakes and ensuring clients get trustworthy data. However, doing so may result in skips for many valid audio matches, and consequently, valuable revenue opportunities could be lost to the content creator or rights holders due to missed monitoring. This reduces the probability of false positives but does not necessarily address fully scalable music monitoring.

Balanced Precision and Recall

When recall improves (from 0.5 to 0.6), the precision decreases to a range between 0.8 and 0.9, becoming a more balanced approach. This scenario is often more realistic for BMAT, as it aims to maximize its detection capabilities while preserving reasonable accuracy. This balance leads to a broader selection of audio content, which is necessary if the goals are comprehensive services in all content and quality. Achieving this balance, BMAT can ensure better music recognition services without overwhelming clients with inaccuracies, making it suitable for dynamic and varied monitoring environments.

High Recall, Low Precision Strategy

However, at higher recall values (above 0.7), the system's precision falls significantly, reaching around 0.32 as recall approaches 0.9. This suggests that while the system captures nearly all possible relevant matches, it also generates a lot of false positives. For BMAT, this strategy might be less desirable, as the high rate of incorrect matches could lead to wrong royalties distribution, leading to client

dissatisfaction, increased verification costs, and potential inefficiencies. Clients may struggle with the volume of false positives, making it harder to discern valuable data.

Ideal Performance: High Precision with at least 75% of Recall

Ideally, when it comes to BMAT, we aim for precision that remains very high, but recall is above 75% at least. This balance helps ensure the system produces suitable quality matches and captures essential items, enabling our music monitoring and recognition services to be fast, reliable and comprehensive. If it could strike a balance, BMAT would produce results of high enough quality that clients felt they were informed without running a significant risk of missing something crucial while concurrently reducing false positive rates. It would create a service that fits BMAT, ensuring the company delivers top-level accuracy and quality in music identification and monitoring solutions.

In summary, while the PR curve demonstrates the trade-offs between precision and recall, BMAT should aim to achieve high accuracy with at least 75% recall. This would ensure that BMAT continues to provide the industry's most accurate, comprehensive, and reliable music recognition services, effectively meeting its clients' diverse needs.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

The best-performing model developed in this dissertation was trained exclusively on speech and dialogue data, explicitly targeting the challenging task of identifying background music in video-on-demand (VoD) content.

The proposed model’s results demonstrate significant advancements over the baseline performance, underscoring the effectiveness of the CueSet dataset and the novel training methodologies employed. Specifically, the model exhibited a +29.9% increase in precision, a +28.3% improvement in recall, and a +28.0% enhancement in F1-score. These metrics reflect a substantial leap forward in the capability of neural network-based audio fingerprinting systems to identify background music within VoD content accurately.

However, while these improvements are meaningful, they also highlight the challenges in this field. While significantly improved, the precision must improve for the near-perfect accuracy required for high-stakes commercial applications. This gap indicates that while the current model represents a considerable advancement, the problem of background music identification in complex audio environments still needs to be fully solved.

The increased recall and F1-score suggest that the model is better at identifying relevant audio segments, but this also comes with the challenge of maintaining precision. This trade-off indicates that further fine-tuning and optimization are needed, particularly in managing the balance between detecting and minimising true positives.

The results from the speech-only model represent a notable advancement in audio fingerprinting, particularly for VoD applications. While the model's precision of 0.83 surpasses previous approaches and meets a minimum viable threshold, but it still falls short of the ideal precision, which should approach 100% for high-stakes applications where accuracy is critical. Achieving such a high level of precision is essential for business use, emphasizing the need for continued research and development to bridge this gap and deliver a truly reliable solution.

6.2 Future Work

Given the results, it is clear that the current model, while promising, does not yet meet the high precision and recall benchmarks necessary for business use, where high accuracy is crucial. Therefore, continued investigation is warranted. Future research should be divided into two key areas:

Exploring Advanced Neural Architectures

Future research should explore more sophisticated neural network models, such as attention mechanisms and transformer architectures, which have shown promise in other domains. These advanced models could help the system better capture intricate patterns in VoD audio, particularly when integrated with additional data modalities like visual information or metadata. Such multimodal integration could provide additional context, further improving model accuracy.

Enhancing Augmentation Techniques and Data Diversity

The experiments revealed that while data augmentation is essential for improving model performance, the specific types of augmentations must be carefully controlled. Enhancing augmentation techniques to simulate real-world audio conditions could significantly improve the model's generalization capabilities. This includes applying more diverse and targeted augmentations, such as incrementally introducing different accents, languages, and speaking styles for speech data. Additionally, methods like noise reduction could be applied in post-processing to mitigate any degradation caused by augmentations.

Optimizing Current Frameworks

Beyond exploring new models, improving the existing framework is crucial. This includes refining indexing and matching algorithms, particularly monitoring complex and variable audio segments in VoD content. Another area for improvement is increasing the segment duration from 1 second to a longer interval, which could enhance the model's contextual understanding. Additionally, developing techniques to filter out or bypass sound effects (SFX) could reduce false positives and improve the accuracy of background music identification.

Error Analysis and Targeted Improvements

Conducting thorough error analysis is vital to identify specific areas where the model struggles, such as particular music genres or background noise. This information can guide the development of more targeted augmentations and interventions. Future research should focus on creating comprehensive error analysis frameworks that quantify and address these challenges systematically.

Integration with Other Audio Analysis Tasks

To build more robust and flexible audio analysis systems, it should be explored to integrate background music identification with other tasks, such as speech recognition, audio tagging, and sound event detection. This multi-task approach could

lead to the development of more comprehensive solutions for various industry use cases.

User Feedback and Adaptive Learning

User feedback and adaptive learning mechanisms could enhance the system’s performance. A model that adapts to different audio environments and user preferences by continually updating based on feedback could lead to more personalized and accurate background music identification systems. Future work should focus on optimizing the use of user-reported input for model refinement.

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Appendix A

Training loss graphs

(a) 06_19_train_aalbas experiment

(b) 06_20_train_aalbas experiment

(c) 06_23_train experiment

(d) 06_28_onlyspeech experiment

(e) 06_30_train_aalbas experiment

(f) 07_03_train_aalbas_noaugdialog experiment

Figure 10: Experiment's Loss graphs